

Equilibrium studies on the complex formation of some bivalent metal ions with 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-Aniline Schiff base and related compounds

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Abstract : The formation constants for the metal chelates with 3-aldehydosalicylic acid-aniline Schiff bases have been determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants follow the Irving-William's order.

Keywords : Stability constant, metal complexes, Schiff bases.

Introduction

The proton-ligand stability constants of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid Schiff base with aniline and related compounds such as *o*-anisidine, *m*-anisidine and *p*-anisidine Schiff bases with 3-aldehydosalicylic acid (Scheme 1) and stability constants of their complexes with bivalent metal ions Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mg^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II} have been determined in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol medium at 25 ± 0.1 °C, at an ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaClO₄). The order of stability constants was found to be in agreement with Irving-Williams order.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The formation curves obtained by plotting average proton number \bar{n}_A vs pH extend over the range $1 < \bar{n}_A$

< 2 show that the H⁺ ion of carboxylic group and one of the phenolic H⁺ ion are dissociated separate steps.

In case of copper titrations a volume of alkali equal to four equivalents of metal ions present in the solution, in excess of that required to neutralize the free perchloric acid, is required to reach pH 3.0 at which the ligand curve departs from the acid curve. The metal ligand curves for zinc, nickel, magnesium, cobalt and cadmium follow the same path and they depart at very low pH of the solution. For all chelating agents the relative positions of the metal curves indicate the relative stabilities of the metal complexes, which follow the Irving-Williams³ order : Zn < Cu > Ni > Co ≈ Cd > Mg.

The metal ligand stability constant are obtained from analysis of average ligand number \bar{n} and pL data. The values of pL at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ correspond to the first and second step stability constants respectively^{1,2}. The log K values calculated for the complexes of all the six metal ions are given in Table 1. The enormously higher log K value for the copper chelate is due to enhanced stabilization arising from John-Teller effect.

Closeness of the log K₁ and log K₂ values of the M²⁺ complexes of the present ligands with the corresponding complexes with salicylic acid⁴, 5-sulfosalicylic acid⁵ and 2-hydroxy-3-methyl salicylic acid⁶, indicate similar mode

Table 1. Proton-ligand and M^{2+} ($M = \text{Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd}$) ligand constants with 3ASAR ligands ($R = \text{H, } o\text{-OCH}_3, m\text{-OCH}_3, p\text{-OCH}_3$) at 25 °C in 50% ethanol-water medium, ionic strength = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)

Ligands	$\log K_n$	H^+	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Cd^{2+}
3ASAA	$\log K_1$	-12.34	7.72	8.20	10.52	8.31	7.80
	$\log K_2$	-3.38	3.85	3.77	6.34	3.87	3.67
3ASAOA	$\log K_1$	-13.12	7.34	8.13	11.79	8.70	7.79
	$\log K_2$	-2.86	5.81	5.35	8.24	6.31	5.91
3ASAMA	$\log K_1$	-13.67	8.03	9.30	13.12	9.43	8.43
	$\log K_2$	-3.01	6.35	6.01	9.41	7.53	6.50
3ASAPA	$\log K_1$	-13.24	7.29	8.04	11.37	8.67	7.83
	$\log K_2$	-2.71	5.80	5.22	8.20	6.10	6.02

of coordination, it is by carboxylate-O and phenolate-O atoms leaving the Schiff base N-atom uncoordinated.

Experimental

All the chemicals including the metal salts, sodium hydroxide, perchloric acid, potassium-bipthalate, borax, EDTA etc., used were of analytical grade. Ethyl alcohol was purified by the method as described by Vogel⁷.

For the first time Schiff bases of 3-aldehydosalicylic acid with aniline, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-anisidine were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of said aldehyde with above aniline and substituted anilines in the alcoholic medium for about 2 h^{8,9}. Schiff bases, thus prepared were more or less strongly coloured and insoluble in water, but soluble in 50% (v/v) water-ethanol solvent medium and in other organic solvents. Purity of the synthesized Schiff bases were confirmed by colour, m.p., elemental analysis and IR spectra.

The concentration of metal ions in each of the metal perchlorates were estimated by complexometric titrations as described by Schwarzenbach¹⁰, by using solutions of $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$ and standard sodium hydroxide.

Magnesium was estimated by titrating it against standard $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$ solution using Erichrome Black T as an indicator. pH-metric titrations were carried out¹¹, following Calvin-Wilson technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti^{1,2}.

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